

THE ESSENCE OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY AND ITS PLACE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. In this study, we clarify the essence of the concept of "cognitive activity" and define it for the field of computer science, and analyze the essence of cognitive activity and its role in the educational process.

Keywords. Knowledge, cognitive activity, essence of knowledge, psychological-pedagogical category, etc.

Introduction. It is impossible to philosophically understand the formation process of the concept of the scientific field of informatics, their essence, educational logic and methods of use.

Cognitive activity consists of the combination (symbiosis) of two concepts: "knowledge" (cognitive activity) and "activity". First of all, from the point of view of the systematic approach, we will distinguish the expanded view of the structural structure of the term "cognitive activity" through such structural concepts as "knowing" and "activity". The concept of "knowing" is one of the main components of symbiosis and has many interpretations depending on the field of research.

Knowing is considered a psychological-pedagogical category, and in this regard, V.Y.Lyaudis said that the activity of knowing is "the activity of self-change, self-development."

For example, in the works of N.I.Pak, knowledge is given the status of the main motivating factor of human development, and it represents an important information process of human activity. In the conditions of global informatization of society, information processes come to the fore in the scientific understanding of philosophy and science.

In the Dictionary of Pedagogy under the editorship of Professor L.M.Luzina, knowledge (knowledge activity) is defined as the need to apply acquired knowledge in practice, that is, it implies the existence of an active component of this process.

Let's move on to the second part of the concept of "cognitive activity". The term "Activity" in a broad sense is defined by the authors as "a functional manifestation of a person in the activities organized, regulated and structured by the subject himself."

Students' activity in the cognitive process has a significant impact on the quality of their cognitive activity. Let us consider the analysis of the third term "activity"

in a similar way. Referring to some sources that interpret this term, we form its definition.

Activity is the active interaction of a person with the outside world, in which he satisfies his needs due to the purposeful effect on the object. The activity reflects the goal, means, result and process. Based on the generalization of the components of "Knowledge - activity - activity" and the definition given above, we will build the structural structure of the concept of "knowledge activity".

Is possible to clarify the essence of students' cognitive activity based on the given generalized structural structure of the concept . Cognitive activity is an integrative structure of a person's action process from the need for knowledge to the achievable result with the help of motivation, educational activity and social regulation.

The analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature shows that there are many interpretations of the concept of cognitive activity. Let's look at some of them:

1. Cognitive activity is "a person's various subjective (curiosity, attentiveness, will, motivation, etc.); goal -oriented complex education acquired, strengthened and developed under the influence of objective (surrounding conditions, teacher's personality, teaching methods and methods) factors ".
2. Cognitive activity is expressed in a person's ability to purposefully and consciously acquire the necessary professional knowledge and constantly improve himself in professional activity.
3. Cognitive activity is "intellectual-emotional response to the learning process, inclination to study, to complete personal joint tasks, interest in working together with the teacher and other students, the desire for practical and intellectual activity that determines the growth in knowledge ".
4. Cognitive activity is considered a personal characteristic manifested in independent, proactive activity, as a result of which professional knowledge is formed.

As can be seen from the above, the content of the concept of cognitive activity changes depending on the context of the research.

In this case, practical interest in some subject, "easiness" of the educational material or positive-emotional, hard-working readiness for the lesson serve as a motive. Motivation is dominated by the appearance type, such as fear of punishment for a bad grade. Practical content (operational component) is presented in the form of minimum learning skills, such as concentration, repetition of previously memorized material, simple thinking operations.

The systematic level of cognitive activity is characterized by the fact that the student realizes the goal of education, he sees opportunities to apply information knowledge in his professional activity only in a narrow specialty area (for example, compiling food calculations in an electronic table), for which active cognitive activity The 2nd type of behavior is typical in the process.

Thus, the structure of cognitive activity in students of the previous situational level develops further: interest in education turns into a stable cognitive warming in relation to the content of the educational material, emotional mood reappears in a general positive attitude towards science.

Basic (basic) knowledge, skills and competences in information science are added to the operational content, students will have the ability to self-assess. In the development of cognitive activity in creative students, the exchange of external motivation (fear of punishment with a grade for uncompleted assignments) to internal motivation (student's reconceptualization of educational goals and perception of personal importance of education) occurs. The student demonstrates independence in setting questions and learning goals; with the help of self-development, initiative is developed in the development of new tasks, problems and methods of solving them. Such students see wide prospects for applying their knowledge of information in their professional activities, as a result of which they perform the 1st behavioral type of cognitive activity.

In the structure of the development of cognitive activity in students presented above, the relationship with information knowledge is observed, and information activity is given through the ability (search, analysis, selection of information).

The student's ability to perform universal learning actions related to perception, understanding, and evaluation of information constitutes the basic minimum of the operational content of cognitive activity.

Knowledge acquired by students in the process of studying informatics is the basis of systematic level development of students' cognitive activity . It should be noted that the successful acquisition of information knowledge, in turn, requires the manifestation of cognitive activity in the lesson.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that there is a two-way relationship between the development of cognitive activity in students and the acquisition of information knowledge. Information knowledge participates (exists) as an important factor in the development of cognitive activity of students. However, the acquisition of this knowledge occurs in the process of learning computer

science, and accordingly, the more active the student is in the lesson, the more successful it is for his formation.

In order to organize the process of teaching informatics according to the approach of cognitive activity in the technical school (to move it to the planned level), the selection of appropriate educational tools that take into account the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of learners is required.

Conclusion. Thus, the essence of the concept of cognitive activity of a technical school student in the process of learning informatics is the integrative structure of the process of personal behavior (from the need for informatics knowledge to the result obtained with the help of educational activity, social regulation motivation (taking into account their characteristics and everyday typology) depending) consists of creating a new motive for knowing each time. Based on it and taking into account the behavioral typology of requirements, a three-level structure of TFB development was developed.

References:

1. Abdullaevna, Sh. K., & Fagimovna, Sh. N. (2020). Non-traditional methods of training Russian language and literature. Water art,(3).
2. Shokarimova, KA (2020). Pedagogical ability and pedagogical of skill education in giving importance . Science and Education, 1(Special Issue 2).
3. Shokarimova, KA (2021). The way of improving reading and writing skills during the lessons. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(2).
4. Davletshin MG, Mavlonov MM, To`ychieva SM –Youth and pedagogical psychology|| T. TDPU, 2009.
5. Safaev NS, Mirashirova NA, Odilova NG –The theory and practice of general psychology||:- T.: TDPU named after Nizomi, 2013.
6. G`ayratovich, E. N. (2022). The Theory of the Use of Cloud Technologies in the Implementation of Hierarchical Preparation of Engineers. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 7, 18-21.
7. Ergashev, N. (2021). METHODS OF USING VISUALIZED EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS IN TEACHING PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES. INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM.
8. G`ayratovich, E. N. (2022). The Problem of Training Future Engineer Personnel on the Basis of Cloud Technology in Technical Specialties of Higher Education. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 13, 1-4.
9. G`ayratovich, E. N. (2022). The Theory of the Use of Cloud Technologies in the Implementation of Hierarchical Preparation of Engineers. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 7, 18-21.